

Recommended citation: Deckert, C., & Mohya, A. (2020). Innovation Without Creativity? - Teaching Creative Problem Solving to Prospective Engineers. In van der Veen, J., van Hattum-Janssen, N., Järvinen, H.-M., de Laet, T., & ten Dam, I. (Eds.), *Engaging Engineering Education. SEFI 48th Annual Conference* (pp. 736-745). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Enschede, The Netherlands. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14654053.

INNOVATION WITHOUT CREATIVITY? – TEACHING CREATIVE PROBLEM SOLVING TO PROSPECTIVE ENGINEERS

Prof. Dr. Carsten Deckert¹

Düsseldorf University of Applied Sciences
Düsseldorf, Germany

Ahmed Mohya

Düsseldorf University of Applied Sciences
Düsseldorf, Germany

Conference Key Areas: *Future engineering skills and talent management, Niche & novel engineering education topics*

Keywords: *Creativity, Innovation, Creative Problem Solving*

ABSTRACT

Engineering can be understood as a sub-category of creative problem solving with a focus on functionality. Engineers are often expected to come up with and implement new and better solutions in a company. The aim of this paper is twofold. Firstly, it gives an overview of the status quo of how creative problem solving is taught at German tertiary institutions (universities and universities of applied sciences). As a result, only a weak reflexive examination of creativity could be detected and only sparse teaching of creativity techniques seems to take place. Secondly, the paper discusses first experiences of teaching creative problem solving in engineering and presents some tentative results on preferences and effectiveness of creativity techniques. The results are derived from a master course with a practical part in which student had to redesign an everyday object using amongst others a range of creativity techniques.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Creativity in Engineering

Creativity is typically defined by the two components of originality and effectiveness [1]. Originality refers to novel attributes of a creative product, while effectiveness signifies the usefulness, appropriateness or value of a creative solution. Creativity plays an important role in engineering, as engineers are often faced with situations in which they need to seek novel solutions for engineering problems.

¹ *Corresponding Author*
C. Deckert
carsten.deckert@hs-duesseldorf.de

This does not only include solutions in innovation management and new product development, but also more mundane aspects of day-to-day work such as, amongst others, production process improvement, logistical challenges as well as repair and maintenance of equipment.

Engineering can even be understood as a special way of creative problem solving. For the field of engineering, Cropley & Cropley [2] suggest the term “functional creativity” to describe the creativity necessary for industrial products such as engineered items or manufactured consumer goods. Functional creativity differs from e.g. expressive creativity of artists by its focus on the useful purpose of novel products. A novel product of engineering must fulfil its intended need and adequately solve an addressed problem. Thus, functionality as part of the effectiveness side of creativity is more important than originality for engineering. Creativity in engineering can be taught by explaining fundamental strategies of creative problem solving and by instructing students in the execution of creativity techniques.

1.2 Creativity Techniques

Creativity techniques are methods or tools which include a set of rules of behaviour and thinking in support of idea generation. They are usually based on idea-generating heuristic principles of association, combination, confrontation and imagination [3]. A major classification of creativity techniques concerns the procedure and distinguishes between intuitive and discursive techniques. While intuitive techniques activate the subconscious mind to spontaneously generate ideas, discursive techniques take a systematic-analytic approach to idea generation [4]. Another major way of classification is into the two principles of creativity by de Bono [5] – or lateral thinking as he calls it – which are generation of alternatives and challenging assumptions. Generation of alternatives includes the idea-generating principles of association and combination, and challenging assumptions contains confrontation and imagination. Fig. 1 shows examples of established creativity techniques according to these classifications.²

Another way to create ideas – especially in invention and product development – is the use of creative heuristics. A creative heuristic can be defined as “a strategy or rule of thumb for generating ideas or for solving problems” [7]. Typical heuristics are the SCAMPER³ checklist and the heuristic principles of the theory of inventive problem solving (TIPS/TRIZ).

² Descriptions of established creativity techniques can be found e.g. in [3], [4] and [6].

³ Acronym for the heuristics: Substitute, Combine, Adapt, Modify, Put to another use, Eliminate, Reverse.

	intuitive	discursive	heuristic
Generation of alternatives	Brainstorming Brainwriting 6-3-5 Method Mindmapping	Morphological box	SCAMPER
Challenging assumptions	Reversal method/ Anti-solution Forced connection	Theory of inventive problem solving (TIPS/TRIZ)	Heuristic principles of TIPS/TRIZ

Fig. 1. Established Creativity Techniques and Heuristics

This paper pursues two research questions: Firstly, it examines the status quo of how creativity is taught in German tertiary institutions by assessing course catalogs. Second, it examines experiences in teaching creativity techniques to prospective engineers in a German master course by assessing the use of creativity techniques by the students.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Assessment of Course Catalogs

The focus of the assessment of course catalogs is on the content of module descriptions of bachelor study programmes in mechanical and process engineering. For the assessment, the course catalogs of the ten largest German universities and the nine largest German universities of applied sciences (plus the university of applied sciences of the authors) in this field were selected. As a criterium for the size of the tertiary institutions the number of students was chosen according to the online prospectus of German universities Studis-online (www.studis-online.de) which is based on data coming directly from the tertiary institutions as well as from the German Federal Agency of statistical data (Statistisches Bundesamt). The analysis did not include private universities and distance universities.

The analysed course catalogs contain in total 818 modules of universities and 649 modules of universities of applied sciences. The content of the module descriptions was analysed with regard to the teaching of creativity. Therefore the mention of key words was checked in the following categories:

- Category 1: Mention of the words “creativity” (in German: “Kreativität”) or “creative” (in German: “kreativ”) in the title of the module
- Category 2: Mention of the words “creativity” or “creative” somewhere else in the module description
- Category 3: Mention of synonymes for “creative” in the module description⁴
- Category 4: Mention of established creativity techniques in the module description⁵

2.2 Assessment of Creativity Techniques

For the assessment of creativity techniques, a master course in industrial engineering at the Düsseldorf University of Applied Sciences (HSD) was analysed. The course took place in the summer semester of 2018 (SS2018). During the course, the prospective engineers worked the entire semester of 14 sessions in groups of five on a self-chosen problem to redesign an everyday object ending with the students presenting their solutions. Participants were students with bachelor degrees in engineering, partly from HSD, partly from other German tertiary institutions. In total, there were 40 students in eight groups. The students were trained during two lectures with exercises in the basics of creative problem solving and creativity techniques and were allowed to choose the number and types of creativity techniques to solve their problem on their own. From the intuitive creativity techniques, the students selected brainstorming as well as brainwriting, 6-3-5 method and mindmapping. From the discursive methods, some of the students used the morphological box, and some students used creative heuristics such as the SCAMPER checklist, the heuristic principles of the theory of inventive problem solving (TIPS/TRIZ) and creative heuristics from one of the authors/the lecturer (see [8]).

Methods of self-assessment and external assessment were used in evaluating the use of creativity techniques. For the self-assessment, a questionnaire was designed with six Likert items evaluating the feeling of being more creative as a person or a team, enhancement of understanding, ease of use, fun of use and expectation to use the technique again. The items were rated on a Likert scale with five response levels. For the external assessment, Consensual Assessment Technique (CAT) was used. CAT is a method to assess the creativity of a given product based on the assumption that a product is creative if suitable independent observers rate it as creative. A suitable observer is usually an expert in the respective field [9][10]. In this specific case five experts on product creativity evaluated the results of the course. The experts were professors and research fellows of the Düsseldorf University of

⁴ Synonymes were taken from the German dictionary Duden: einfallsreich, erfinderisch, erfindungsreich, fantasie reich, fantasievoll, findig, geistreich, genial, gestalterisch, ideenreich, künstlerisch, originell, produktiv, schöpferisch, ingeniös, konstruktiv, innovativ.

⁵ The modules were checked for the following established creativity techniques: brainstorming, mindmapping, 6-3-5 method, six thinking hats, morphological box/matrix, theory of inventive problem solving (TIPS/TRIZ), forced connection and synectics. These techniques cover the main idea-generating principles of association, combination and confrontation and contain intuitive as well as discursive techniques.

Applied Sciences who lecture and research in the fields of new product development and innovation management.

In a second master course held during the summer semester of 2019 (SS2019) the prospective engineers again worked the entire semester of 14 sessions in groups on a self-chosen problem to redesign an everyday object. In total, there were 28 students working in five groups. The students were again trained during two lectures with exercises in the basics of creative problem solving and creativity techniques. This time, however, students were forced to use brainwriting pool as a creativity technique from the category “generation of alternatives” and reversal method/anti-solution as a technique from the category “challenging of assumptions”. This means that the students only used intuitive techniques to better compare the effect of the two categories. For the self-assessment, the same questionnaire as in SS2018 was used again. No external assessment was taken to evaluate the creativity of the results, as all the students used the same techniques. Additionally, data was collected on the degree of familiarity with established creativity techniques.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Creativity in Course Catalogs

The results of the assessment of the course catalogs are summarized in table 1. Neither of the analysed universities and universities of applied sciences have a course with the term “creativity” or “creative” in the title. This means that there are no courses in the tertiary institutions in mechanical and process engineering exclusively dedicated to creativity or creative problem solving. In the universities twenty modules (2% of the modules) contained the terms in the module description and ten modules (1%) contained synonymes. In universities of applied sciences only twelve modules (2%) included the terms, but 49 modules (8%) included synonymes. The most common synonym used was “konstruktiv” (constructional) followed by “innovativ” (innovative). This shows that creativity in engineering is often associated with the theory of design (in German: “Konstruktionslehre”).

Table 1. Absolute and relative rate of modules in the respective category

	Category 1: Creativity in the module title	Category 2: Creativity in the module description	Category 3: Synonymes in the module description	Category 4: Creativity techniques in the module description
Universities	0 (0%)	20 (2%)	10 (1%)	2 (0.2%)
Universities of applied sciences	0 (0%)	12 (2%)	49 (8%)	6 (1%)

Creativity techniques were only mentioned in two modules of universities (0.2%) and in six modules of universities of applied sciences (1%). Eight of the ten universities and five of the ten universities of applied sciences do not have a single course with

creativity techniques in the module description. Universities of applied sciences have more courses with creativity techniques which probably reflects their stronger orientation to practical experience (“applied sciences”). The most common techniques were morphological box and TIPS. This also shows that creativity is associated with the design process which is the main area of application for the morphological box. Furthermore it shows a preference for discursive techniques.

Our analysis shows that there seems to be no reflexive examination and deliberation of creativity in mechanical and process engineering. In all the course catalogs analysed, there was not a single course about creativity or creative problem solving. The majority of these tertiary institutions do not even teach creativity techniques – at least they do not advertise it in their module descriptions. As there are courses on innovation management and product development, this indicates that the expectations for engineers are to generate innovation without creativity. The significance of these results is limited insofar as the analysis only focusses on the content of modules and not on the procedure of teaching (e.g. method of instruction, method of examination). However, it could be argued that for an important skill an entire course or a large part of a course should be reserved to enable instruction, reflection and discussion of the subject.

3.2 Creativity Techniques for Prospective Engineers

The results of the self-assessment in SS2018 are displayed in the chart in fig. 2. It shows that intuitive creativity techniques have the highest scores on most criteria. Most of the students think they are more creative personally and in group when they use these techniques (both 1st rank). They also find them fun (1st rank) and easy (2nd rank) to use. So they are likely to use these methods again (1st rank). Discursive techniques fare best in the criteria ease of use (1st rank) and fun (a close 2nd rank). Heuristics show the best result in fostering the understanding of creativity and the creative process (1st rank). The students rank heuristics higher than discursive techniques on the criteria of fostering creativity of individuals and groups, but lowest on the criteria for fun and ease of use.

Fig. 2. Self-assessment (SS2018, percentage of answers “agree” and “strongly agree” for students who used the respective creativity techniques)

In the external assessment, the groups who used creativity techniques from several categories fare better than the ones who only used intuitive techniques. The groups who only used intuitive techniques are ranked on the last three places from all eight groups. Especially the combination of intuitive techniques with discursive or heuristic techniques shows promising results. Usually the students used the intuitive techniques first to generate a great number of ideas and then switched to more systematic-analytic approaches to refine their ideas. This result is however restricted by the small number of groups and the fact that not all combinations could be tested, since the students chose the techniques on their own. So there were no groups who chose to use only discursive techniques or heuristics and no group combined discursive techniques with heuristics.

In SS2019 the students were forced to use brainwriting pool and reversal method/anti-solution. So the self-assessment includes only these two methods (see fig. 3). It is striking that brainwriting is ranked higher on all criteria except for ease of use where both methods achieved almost the same approval. Most students think that brainwriting makes them and their team more creative, enhances their understanding of creativity and is fun and easy to use. Only a minority of students thinks the same for the reversal method. This might indicate a preference of engineering students for methods that generate alternatives over methods that challenge assumptions. As students used brainwriting first and the reversal method after that, the sequence of use might have impacted the assessment. Some students said that the reversal method gave them next to no new ideas after brainwriting.

Fig. 3. Self-assessment (SS2019, percentage of answers “agree” and “strongly agree” for students who used the respective creativity techniques)

The assessment of the degree of familiarity in fig. 4 shows that the students are intimately familiar with the intuitive techniques of brainstorming and mindmapping and the discursive technique of morphological box. The latter is often part of the subjects on theory of design in the bachelor study programme. There is only a medium familiarity with the concept of brainwriting. The familiarity with techniques from the category “generation of alternatives” (brainstorming, brainwriting, morphological box, mindmapping) is much stronger than the familiarity with techniques from the category “challenging assumptions” (reversal method/anti-solution, forced connection, TIPS/TRIZ, synectics and six thinking hats). Especially, there is no prior experience with the reversal method which might have impacted the assessment.

Fig. 4. Degree of familiarity with creativity techniques (SS2019)

Overall, different techniques have different strengths and weaknesses, and a combination of methods from different categories of procedure (intuitive and discursive/heuristic) seems to be most suitable to break up the usual systematic-analytic way of thinking of prospective engineers. The impact of different categories of idea-generating principles (generation of alternatives and challenging assumptions) is still somewhat unclear and needs further clarification.

Engineering students, however, tend to favor discursive techniques and techniques which use generation of alternatives as an idea-generating principle. So, it is important for a course on creativity in engineering to make students try out different methods and reflect on their strengths and weaknesses and on their possible areas of application. The significance of these results is limited insofar as the experiments were imbedded in a regular course with some restrictions in comparison to laboratory conditions (compulsory attendance, grading, free or limited choice of methods, low number of groups). However, the advantage of this approach is that it examines engineering students under realistic conditions over a long period of time on a realistic task instead of a shortterm laboratory experiment under artificial conditions. As Sutherland [11] writes: "True creativity is not thinking of a hundred uses for a brick: it is the ability to solve new problems [...]".

REFERENCES

- [1] Runco M.A. and Jaeger G.J. (2012), The Standard Definition of Creativity, *Creativity Research Journal*, Vol. 24, No. 1, pp. 92-96.
- [2] Cropley, D.H. and Cropley, A.J. (2010), Functional Creativity, "Products" and the Generation of Effective Novelty, In Kaufman J.C., Sternberg R.J. (eds.), *The Cambridge Hand-book of Creativity*, Cambridge University Press, New York, pp. 301-317.
- [3] Geschka, H. and Zirm, A. (2011), Kreativitätstechniken (Creativity Techniques). In S. Albers & O. Gassmann (eds.), *Handbuch Technologie- und Innovationsmanagement (Handbook Technology and Innovation Management)*, Gabler, Wiesbaden, pp. 279–302.
- [4] Brem, A. and Brem, S. (2013), *Kreativität und Innovation im Unternehmen: Methoden und Workshops zur Sammlung und Generierung von Ideen (Creativity and Innovation in the Company: Methods and Workshops to Collect and Generate Ideas)*. Schäffer-Poeschel, Stuttgart, pp. 23-38.
- [5] De Bono, E. (1990), *Lateral Thinking*, Penguin, London.
- [6] Ahmed, P.K. and Shepherd, C.D. (2010), *Innovation Management*, FT Prentice Hall, Harlow, pp. 64-73.
- [7] Weber, R.J. (1992), *Forks, Phonographs and Hot Air Balloons, A Field Guide to Inventive Thinking*, Oxford University Press, New York, Oxford.
- [8] Deckert, C. (2018), Creative Heuristics in Engineering Education, In SEFI (eds.), *Proceedings of the 46th SEFI Annual Conference "Creativity, Innovation and Entrepreneurship for Engineering Education Excellence"* (724-731), SEFI, Brüssel.
- [9] Hennessey B.A., Amabile T.M. and Mueller J.S. (2011), Consensual Assessment, In: Runco M.A. and Pritzker S.R. (eds.) *Encyclopedia of Creativity (Second Edition, vol. 1)*. Academic Press, San Diego, pp. 253-260.
- [10] Baer, J. and McKool, S.S. (2009), Assessing Creativity Using the Consensual Assessment Technique, In C.S. Schreiner (ed.), *Handbook of Research on Assessment Technologies, Methods, and Applications in Higher Education*, IGI Global, DOI: 10.4018/978-1-60566-667-9, pp. 65-77.
- [11] Sutherland, S. (2007), *Irrationality*, Printer & Martin, London, p. 89.